

Electrode Photopotential : Part II.

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Photopotentials obtained by irradiating a metal electrode in benzophenone and methoxysubstituted benzophenones in ethanol are investigated. The maximum photopotentials obtained are shown to vary linearly with respect to logarithm of intensity of irradiation. 4-4'-dimethoxybenzophenone is shown to give enhanced value of $\Delta \phi_{max}$ than benzophenone while 4-methoxy and 3-4 dimethoxy benzophenone give much smaller values. A mechanism for the production of photopotentials due to the formation of an intermediate is suggested.

Photopotentials produced as a result of irradiating a nonaqueous solution containing acetophenone have been reported by us¹. It was shown that photopotentials were dependent on the nature of the electrode material. The cause of the photopotential was attributed to the formation of a short lived intermediate in the photochemical reaction between acetophenone and the solvent. This paper reports further work using benzophenone as solute. The dependence of photopotential on substitution in benzophenone is studied.

EXPERIMENTAL

The experimental arrangement was the same as used previously. Benzophenone used was Narden Pure grade purified by twice recrystallisation from ethanol. 4-4' dimethoxy benzophenone, 3-4 dimethoxy benzophenone and 4-methoxy benzophenone were prepared according to standard procedure and were purified rigorously by crystallisation from ethanol, and vacuum dried. Melting points of the above compounds were 147°, 105°, and 60° respectively.

Preliminary experiments showed the aprotic solvents like CCl_4 , benzene and cyclohexane gave very low values of photopotentials while highest values were obtained using ethanol and n-propanol. In the experiments reported here, purified ethanol was used as solvent. It was necessary to deoxygenate the solution thoroughly till a constant and reproducible value of photopotential was obtained which was recorded. Reproducibility in repeated runs was better than ± 5 millivolts. Electrodes used were platinum, gold plated platinum, silver, copper plated on silver and nickel.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The rise and decay of photopotential as obtained in the case of 0.01 *M* solutions of benzophenone, 4-methoxy benzophenone, 3-4 methoxy benzophenone and 4-4' dimethoxy benzophenone are shown in figure 1. The substitution of methoxy group

Figure 1. Growth and decay of photopotential.
 (1) 0.1 *M* BP., (2) 0.1 *M* 4-4' dimethoxy BP.,
 (3) 0.1 *M* 4-methoxy BP. and (4) 0.1 *M* 3-4
 dimethoxy BP. in ethanol

in one of the benzene rings reduces the maximum value of photopotential considerably. This observation is on par with that made by Surash and Hercules² who observed that 4-bromo benzophenone gave a smaller value of $\Delta\phi_{\max}$ than pure benzophenone. The enhancement of the value of $\Delta\phi_{\max}$ in the case of two methoxy groups in para position is a pertinent observation since it has been shown that methyl substitution in the two para positions also enhances this value. It can be concluded from these observations that in the case of benzophenone, substitution of one or more groups in the same benzene ring reduces the value of $\Delta\phi_{\max}$ while para position substitution increases it.

The electrode material is an important factor which determines the extent of the value of $\Delta\phi_{\max}$ as will be evident from table I. Highest values are obtained using platinum as active electrode while readily oxidisable electrodes give smaller values of $\Delta\phi_{\max}$.

2. J. J. Surash and D. M. Hercules, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1962, 66, 1602.

TABLE I

 $\Delta\phi_{\max}$ in millivolts (BP : Benzophenone)

Electrode	BP	3-4 dimethoxy BP	4-4' dimethoxy BP	4-methoxy BP
Platinum	-330	-130	-358	-224
Gold	-180	-60	-195	-176
Silver	-52	-30	-72	-54
Nickel	-14	-7	-21	-15
Copper	-5	nil	-15	nil

The value of $\Delta\phi_{\max}$ is dependent on the intensity of irradiation. This was tested by using successive apertures in an iris diaphragm placed in the path of incident light. Relative intensities at each setting were measured by means of a photoelectric cell connected to a sensitive microammeter. Intensities were measured relative to full incident beam reckoned as 100. Figure 2 shows the dependence of $\Delta\phi_{\max}$ in the case

Figure 2. Dependence of photopotential on logarithm of intensity.
 -0.1 M 4-4' dimethoxy BP. ; -0.1 M BP. ; -0.1 M acetophenone in ethanol.

of benzophenone and 4-4' dimethoxy benzophenone on logarithm of intensity. Results obtained with acetophenone are also shown in the figure. It is clear that $\Delta\phi_{\max}$ varies linearly as $\log I$.

TABLE II

Electrode : Platinum	
Benzophenone concentration : 0.01 M	
Solvent	$\Delta\phi_{\max}$
Ethanol	-330 m. v.
Isopropanol	-245 m. v.
Chloroform	-25 m. v.
Carbon tetrachloride	nil

TABLE III

*Electrode : Platinum**Solvent : Ethanol*

Solute	Unfiltered light*	Filtered light@	Visible light B
Benzophenone	-330 m. v.	-130 m. v.	-5 m. v.
4-4' Dimethoxy benzophenone	-355 m. v.	-330 m. v.	-5 m. v.

* Unfiltered light : Mercury arc in quartz 2300-7000 \AA .

@ Filtered light : Filter used was quartz cell containing 10% CuSO_4 in water slightly acidified. Transmitted 3000-4000 \AA .

B Visible light : Green (.5300 \AA) glass filter.

Table II gives the effect of solvent on the value of $\Delta\phi_{\text{max}}$. It is clear that in aprotic solvents photopotentials are not observed. This observation runs parallel to the fact that there is no photochemical reaction between benzophenone and aprotic solvents. Table III shows the effect of different wavelength regions on the value of $\Delta\phi_{\text{max}}$. No photopotentials are observed using visible light.

From Table III, it is clear that in case of 4-4' dimethoxy benzophenone, there is only slight reduction in the value of $\Delta\phi_{\text{max}}$, while with benzophenone, the reduction is considerable on cutting off radiation below 3000 \AA . It is also seen that visible light does not produce any change in potentials. Figure 3 gives the absorption spectra

Figure 3. Absorption spectra of
 Curve 1 : Benzophenone
 Curve 2 : 4-4' dimethoxybenzophenone

for benzophenone and 4-4' dimethoxy benzophenone from which it is clear that in the case of benzophenone there is strong absorption below 3000 \AA while the maximum of absorption band of 4-4' dimethoxy benzophenone lies at 2950 \AA . If the phenomena of photopotential is to depend on the absorption characteristics of the solute, one

could predict a considerable lowering in $\Delta\phi_{\max}$ for benzophenone and a small lowering in case of 4-4' dimethoxy benzophenone, which is actually the case.

Photopotentials are produced as a result of photochemical reaction between the ketone and the solvent resulting in the formation of free radical or an unstable product which may diffuse away from the electrode or the free radical may undergo secondary reactions. The formation of ketyl radical in the case of benzophenone/alcohol system in neutral solutions has been reported by Porter and coworkers³ while Pitts⁴ gives evidence for the formation of a radical intermediate consequent on the formation of ketyl radical.

The possible photochemical reactions can be ($\phi : C_6H_5$)

Reaction (1) represents formation of triplet state while (2) represents H-abstraction reaction; reaction (3) represents the formation of ketyl radical anion for which Porter³ (et al) has given definite evidence in his work; (4), (5) and (6) represents the dimerisation reaction. Reaction (6) according to Porter is possible only in high alkaline media. The cause of the photopotential is surely the formation of some electroactive species after irradiation. 4-4' Dimethoxy benzophenone is shown (et al) to undergo similar reaction sequence giving a much higher yield of dimer than in the case of benzophenone. This observation runs parallel to the fact that $\Delta\phi_{\max}$ is much larger in the 4-4' substituted benzophenone than in the case of benzophenone. Reaction (3) being reversible, the decay of photopotential on removing the source of irradiation is expected. The potentials produced are not due to the formation of pinacol was demonstrated by adding the pinacol. Since the value of $\Delta\phi_{\max}$ did not

3. A. Beckett and G. Porter, *Trans. Farad. Soc.*, 1963, **59**, 2038; 1964, **60**, 873.

4. J. N. Pitts, R. L. Letsinger, R. P. Taylor and J. M. Patterson, *J. A. C. S.*, 1959, **81**, 1068.

change, it was concluded that benzophenone/pinacol is not the electroactive couple. The electroactive species can probably be a ketyl radical anion/benzophenone couple, so that one could write an expression,

$$E = E^{\circ} + \frac{RT}{F} \ln \frac{[\phi_2 \text{CO}]}{[\phi \text{CO}]^-} \quad \dots \quad (7)$$

if Nernst equation is to be obeyed. However the possibility of photochemical products adsorbing on the electrode thus changing the electrode potential cannot however be ignored. Assuming that (7) is applicable, it is clear that the potential will depend on the intensity of radiation, a linear plot of $\log I$ against $\Delta\phi_{\max}$ is realised⁵.

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5. J. C. Ghosh, *Z. Physik. Chem.*, 1929, **33**, 419.